

THE METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES AT MEDICAL UNIVERSITIES

Utambetova Arzayim Kalmurzaevna

Tashkent Medical Academy

Teacher of the department

Pedagogy, psychology and Foreign languages

Annotation. This article examines the methodology of foreign language teaching, the history of its development, the types of modern interactive methods used in the methodology of foreign language teaching, and issues of their application.

Keywords: speech activity, innovation, communication skills, skills, competences, didactics, intercultural communication, speech skills

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается методика преподавания иностранного языка, история ее развития, виды современных интерактивных методов, используемых в методике преподавания иностранного языка, и вопросы их применения.

Ключевые слова: речевая деятельность, инновация, коммуникативные навыки, умения, компетенции, дидактика, межкультурное общение, речевые навыки

Nowadays, learning foreign languages is becoming more popular. Ensuring the quality of teaching foreign languages to the young generation, fundamentally improving the system of training specialists who can speak foreign languages fluently, and training mature personnel who meet world educational standards by mastering foreign languages one of the goals of reform.

This is an integral part of professional training of specialists. The quality of their language training depends on the successful resolution of professional growth issues and leads to the expansion of relations with foreign partners. Knowledge of a foreign language, which allows continuing the professional potential, studies during

university and post-secondary education, as well as self-success, largely depends on the way of working. It is necessary to use modern methods in order to ensure the implementation of measures to improve the level and quality of training of qualified medical personnel who have acquired foreign languages for medical institutions of higher education.

At the same time, one can say that every language has its own rules and secrets. Based on this, introducing students to the basics, modern methods of teaching foreign languages, with other subjects that are fundamental to the methodology, and in many ways determines its modern content and other status. The ability to evaluate the existing concepts of foreign language teaching in general education and scientific subjects, to introduce students to techniques, methods, tools, to learn and to develop the ability to use them effectively and creatively will help to develop the future professional activities of students.

Because of studying the methodology course, students master the current trends of methodology development, content and structure, foreign language teaching systems, interaction features. Currently, more and more attention paid to the issues of teaching a foreign language as a language of professional communication, where reading original medical literature is the main source of obtaining the latest information of a special nature, which increases the specificity will help.

Thus, the relevance of research depends on the following factors:

- Lack of evidence-based approach and methods in teaching foreign language to medical students;
- Low effectiveness of practical developments in teaching foreign languages as professionally important skills of future doctors;
- The priority of reading special texts in a foreign language at a medical university;
- The insufficient development of the methodology of teaching medical students to study, taking into account the specific characteristics of professional training in medical universities;

- Low level of study skills by medical students.

For students studying in medical universities, the subject of foreign language teaching, the process and methods of education, the science of teaching a foreign language, the study of teacher and student activities considered a subject of the methodology. In modern conditions, serious requirements placed on the training level of any specialist. A very important and important component of this preparation is knowledge of a foreign language. The state standard of higher professional education requires taking into account professional characteristics when studying foreign languages at non-specialized universities.

It provides a professionally oriented approach to learning and aims to develop students' communication skills and readiness in professional, business and academic fields.

Learning a foreign language should take into account the specifics of professional thinking, the personal needs of students, and the development of their personal qualities. These aspects are extremely important in the organization of the educational process at the medical university. Learning a foreign language is a multifaceted discipline, in which a person undergoes complex psychological changes.

In particular, the process of comparing the native language with a foreign language occurs. Various teaching methods and technologies used in this process. With the help of modern pedagogical technologies, teaching by comparing the foreign language with the mother tongue gives an effective result.

Teaching a foreign language requires knowledge of its methodology. Methodology and technology are important in the process of learning a foreign language. There are various methods of teaching methodology. The widely used methods in foreign language teaching methodology are communicative didactic method, intercultural dialogue organization method and exercise organization method.

All three methods closely related and complement each other. Since the science of methodology related to the science of didactics, communicativeness during foreign language learning and the method of communicative didactics created. The general cultural competence of a medical professional in a foreign language should reflect the readiness and ability to master a foreign language in the field of daily and professional communication in order to carry out certain types of professional activities: hours of standards.

As a regional component, such foreign language courses be introduced not only in the first courses, but also in the higher courses (as an elective or additional), where the experience of the department of foreign languages of medical universities shows that students prefer to learn a foreign language more encouraged.

The next important aspect of the practice of teaching a foreign language at a medical university is ethical. The ethical component is an integral part of the education and training process, which ensures that students acquire a number of professional qualities and values during the training process, which based on the desire to put the needs of the patient first.

From the point of view of state educational standards, foreign language is one of the mandatory components of humanitarian training of a specialist in a medical university. According to the program of the subject "Foreign language in medicine", in English classes, students are acquainted with the basics of the English language and the necessary professional vocabulary. They read texts containing special vocabulary and develop dialogic speech. During each lesson, students develop the most important and useful information, skills and competencies of a foreign language as a means of communication.

In solving this problem, active pedagogical teaching methods come to the fore, which encourages students independently and creatively master the material. An example of this is a conference held by foreign language teachers.

Conclusion. The main goal of forming the professional and personal culture of medical students is the development of socially important qualities as the highest

value of education. A doctor's professional and personal culture should permeate all aspects of his professional activity. In this regard, the most urgent problem of the educational process at the higher medical school is to form the personality of the future doctor, to pay more attention to his civic responsibility, legal culture, spirituality, initiative in foreign languages.

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